

CHARACTERISTICS OF OCCASIONAL COMPOUNDS IN DIFFERENT SYSTEMIC LANGUAGES

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Annotation: Features such as language units, words and word combinations, singularity and occasionality are important in the development and progress of the language. This article explores the special features of occasionality combinations in structured languages. Occasionalism is an area that is important at the same time in the fields of linguistics, literary studies, and stylistics. This article highlights the peculiarities of casualness and uniqueness.

Key words: occasionality, singularity, lexical, phraseological unity, generality, specificity.

Language as the most important means of communication in human life, together with the historical progress of society, is constantly changing and developing. Ultimately, we can say that language is an open system with a dynamic character. V.Gumboldt and F. Sossyur, who took note of the dynamic nature of language, had argued that in it an Antinomy of invariance and variability is practiced. From this it can be understood that each level of the language, along with stable, central units, which have been preserved since long periods as the identity, spiritual heritage of the people, is characteristic of a certain period of the historical development of the language, and also has border units located around central units. So, in continuous development, each level of the language in which it is growing is counted as a system consisting of a relationship of Central and border units. The more necessary the study of stable units for Linguistics, the more significant the study of variable units, since, both are the most basic integral parts of the language. In particular, from the periodic stages of linguistics, it can be seen that some of the variable units can be ranked among the stable units as periods pass, or, conversely, some can go out of consumption in the short term while maintaining the provisional designation. We can also classify occasionalist compounds into these types.

Occasionalisms are said to have special uses, which have not become popular in the general language. We can say many linguistic scientists of our country and the world who have conducted research in this area. Of These, S. Sultonsaidova, O'. Sharipova, Z. Alimova, Sh. Imomovs research work is noteworthy, in addition, A.E.Mamatov's doctoral dissertation "Problems of lexical and phraseological norm in modern Uzbek literary language" (1991), It is no exaggeration to say that the likes of S. Toshaliyeva's candidate thesis "okkazionalisms in Uzbek" (1998) further enriched the stylistics of the Uzbek language. In addition, Uzbek literature can also be of particular importance in the works of many writers, poets, in particular in the poems of Omon Matjon.

The properties of "short duration" and "constancy" allow units to be divided into continuous and occasional types. While Continuity shows the traditional approach in the work, occasionalism can express identity, belonging to exactly one author or only one situation.

Since "continuity-occasionality" is one of the determining factors in the dynamic aspect of a language, studying the state of a particular language at a certain period in this aspect also provides a favorable opportunity to highlight the feature of "continuity – variability" in the evolutionary improvement of the language. Each period has great sages, and in the products of the creation of these sages, we see the commonality and privity inherent in this period. In the case of generality – continuity, specificity is researched in the manner of occasionality.

These scribes, in addition to taking advantage of the rich possibilities of the native language in their works, themselves contribute to the enrichment and development of this language. The individual linguistic units created by each author also take place from the composition of the changing units of the language of the same period. The words created by the people are referred to in linguistics as the okkazionalism of oral speech, and the words created by a particular creator are characteristic of individual –individual speech, that is, artistic okkazionalisms.

Non-universal is a word or a combination of words with an individual and specific meaning newly created by the creators, and only the language units used in this text are called okkazionality. The opposite concept of occasionality is continuity, according to which the units used in the text, speech, poetry or baddic discourse are unique only to this given situation. This is especially evident in the process of word making. Examples include a Statehouse (Government House), Gazetteer (editorial), barracks (maternity ward), Bell-House (multi-telephone room), townspeople (builders), call (government note), tribulation (condolence), dildosh. world. spiritualist. lexical units such as the pilgrim can be clear evidence of our thought. Such lexicons also include dialectisms, terms, kansclarisms, jargon, and Argos. Bulaming all represents a stylistic meaning in artistic, publicistic, colloquial styles from functional style types.

Occasionality is also widely used in the publicistic method. Because for the degree of originality and prevalence of the given text, this particular genre is the same. It uses simple sentences from the types of sentences, mostly short, expressing loanwords. Compound statements, on the other hand, help to show a logical connection, to form a holistic, general picture of one event or another. Accordingly, one type of sentence or another is used according to the nature of the material being published in the press. In reportage, there is a very compactness of the sentence, a change in the construction of the sentence according to the speech situation. Because the events being reported in the reportage are often one replacing the other. Therefore, it is appropriate to compose compact sentences for them.

In place of the conclusion, we can say that okkazionaliz is a word that is randomly generated or used only once. They are able to raise the level of a work to a higher level, even if they are used precisely for a particular text or work and do not apply again. as such, okkazionalism is the product of each creator's own true creation, which is the product of his creator.

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